

Speech Acts of Praise in English Pedagogical Discourse

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ABSTRACT

Pedagogical discourse refers to the institutional type of communication, which is based on status-role relations. The goal of pedagogical discourse is the socialization of a new member of society. The main participants in the pedagogical discourse are the student and the teacher. The functions of discourse interact in the real pedagogical space and they can be correlated with the main functions of the teacher's activity: teaching, educating and developing.

Keywords: discourse, pedagogical discourse, communication, teacher's activity, discourse interact.

INTRODUCTION

In modern social sciences and communicative linguistics, the term "discourse" has a large number of interpretations. There are several approaches to the interpretation of this concept. For example, Deborah Schiffrin distinguishes three main approaches to the interpretation of the term discourse:

1. Discourse as "a language above the level of a sentence or phrase."
2. Discourse as "any use of language".
3. Discourse as a "statement".

Such a definition suggests that discourse is not considered the simplest set of disparate lexical units of the "more than a sentence" construction, but a single combination of language units that are functionally oriented and determined by a certain context.

In sociolinguistics, discourse is defined as "the communication of people, considered from the standpoint of their belonging to a particular social group or in relation to a particular typical situation".

Pedagogical discourse refers to the institutional type of communication, which is based on status-role relations.

DISCUSSIONS

The main participants of the pedagogical discourse are the student and the teacher, acting in various conditions of communication. A distinctive feature of pedagogical discourse is the significant inequality of communication participants.

It is known that a person from childhood learns the language and, along with it, the culture of his people. All the subtleties of the culture of the people are reflected in their language, which is specific and unique, as it captures the world and the person in it in different ways. In this regard, the significance and relevance of intercultural communication as a science and the intercultural competence that it teaches is quite obvious. When it comes to communication, especially intercultural communication, it can be very difficult to draw a line between the sociological and psychological aspects of communication. Both those and others deal with complex categories arising in the process of communication or transmitted through it - values, motives, attitudes, stereotypes and prejudices. And all these categories directly affect the communicative behavior of a particular linguistic personality [1]. These pragmatic aspects of verbal communication are dealt with by the so-called cross-cultural pragmatics, the tool of which is a comparative analysis of individual principles that characterize communicative activity and the corresponding cultural scenarios. Having studied the theory of speech acts, we can argue that a speech act is a purposeful speech action performed in accordance with the principles and rules of speech behavior adopted in a given society. The very construction of a speech act in its leading features is a model of a normal, non-speech action: it contains an intention, a goal, and a result. The main characteristic of a speech act is its illocutionary force, i.e. communicative intention that underlies the utterance of a particular statement.

Evaluative expressions are acts whose purpose is to evoke an emotional reaction in the interlocutor. Evaluation is a linguistic expression that demonstrates the relationship of the interlocutor to the real object. Evaluation largely depends on the satisfaction of the speaker's needs, interests and goals.

Having considered the features of speech acts of a positive assessment, we can derive the definition of a speech act of praise - this is a communicative action that expresses a positive assessment, approval or admiration of an object or its activities. We can also conclude that the speech acts of approval, praise, compliment and flattery have in common a positive assessment of the addressee or the subject that falls into the evaluation field. Among the most important and, at the same time, culturally contradictory pragmatic principles, it is necessary to note **309**

"Principle of Politeness" by P. Brown and S. Levinson and numerous works devoted to speech acts, one way or another built on this principle - these include speech acts of praise / compliment . Cross-cultural differences are manifested, in particular, in what type of politeness - based on solidarity or on maintaining a distance - is characteristic of a given culture [2].

Cross-cultural pragmatics differs from traditional, proper linguistic comparative studies of the categories of politeness, forms of reference and address, analysis of speech acts, primarily by its functional orientation. Which communicative strategy will be chosen, in which particular cultural scenario this or that statement will be embodied, depends on the cultural characteristics of the corresponding communicative community [1]. Thus, intercultural communication has a pronounced applied orientation. This is not only a science, but also a set of skills that can and should be mastered. And first of all, these skills are necessary for those whose professional activities are associated with interaction with different cultures, when mistakes and communication failures lead to failures in negotiations, to inefficient work of the team, to social tension. This confirms the relevance of this thesis, which is devoted to the study of the features of speech acts of praise/compliment in modern communicative cultures.

Since praise involves the expression of the evaluative attitude of the subject / subjects to another subject / subjects, it is necessary to dwell on the concept of "evaluative speech acts", and also consider the category of evaluation.

As Rakhilina E.V. notes, "no concept in the language finds such a variety of classifications, such diverse approaches to analysis, such a multitude of interpretations and such a brilliant constellation of researchers in the history of linguistic teachings from antiquity to the present, as assessment."

The evaluation category in its essence has a connection with the ontology of human consciousness, its interpretive function and reflects the interpretative model of the world. They embody the ways of interpreting information by a person and fix the means of this interpretation in the language system in the form of an unambiguous knowledge format. The evaluation category has a relative nature, dependent on other conceptual objects, and in its structure displays a combination of different principles of organization.

The category of evaluation in linguistics is understood as a set of multi-level language units connected by evaluative semantics and expressing the positive or negative attitude of the author to the subject of speech.

Evaluation as a value aspect of meaning can be expressed in language in different ways. According to the concept of E.M.Wolf, the evaluation can be limited to elements smaller than the word, but it can characterize both a group of words and the whole statement.

The study of evaluative speech acts is of great interest for modern linguistics, which has been characterized by an anthropocentric orientation over the past decades. The analysis of the functional semantics of evaluation is reflected in the complex works of N. D. Arutyunova, A. A. Ivin, E. M. Volf, T. V. Bulygina, A. D. Shmelev, A. A. Romanov and others.

When classifying evaluative speech acts, the problem arises of determining the criteria by which it was possible to describe them.

This problem is complicated by the presence of the phenomenon of implicit evaluation contained in verbs with a distinct illocutionary function.

So, E.M. Wolf believes that evaluative expressions are acts "the purpose of which is to cause a perlocutionary effect in the interlocutor - an emotional reaction" [Wolf 2006: 166]. The researcher classifies them as expressives.

The selection of an emotional reaction as an effect of the impact of a speech act on the addressee as a criterion for belonging to an evaluative speech act, in our opinion, is not entirely correct, since many speech acts expressing an assessment may not be aimed at changing the emotional state of the addressee. Such acts can rather be attributed to emotive speech acts, where emotivity is the verbal expression of emotions.

Speech acts, the illocutionary orientation of which is somehow connected with the evaluative activity of the speaker, can be classified as evaluative. In the case of using direct evaluative speech acts, their distinguishing feature is the presence of an evaluative relationship in the propositional content of the statement, and when speech acts are performed with an accompanying evaluation, the evaluative relationship is present only in the form of logical or pragmatic presuppositions. So, for direct evaluative acts, the presence of the speaker's evaluative attitude is the main thing. Therefore, speech acts of praise, approval or censure can be attributed to this type of speech acts.

As we can see in the above definitions, the words approval and praise, compliment and flattery intersect in their semantics. It is not possible to distinguish between praise and approval based only on definitions, since one phenomenon is explained at the expense of the other. In the definitions of a compliment, the senses "courtesy", "pleasantness", "politeness", as well as "admiration" appear, which makes it possible already at the stage of lexical interpretation

identify the etiquette and pretentious nature of the compliment, implying admiration. In the dictionary definitions of flattery, our attention is drawn to the senses “insincerity”, “hypocrisy”, “compliance”, which distinguish this phenomenon from related speech acts. Statements of flattery always work as a means of achieving the selfish goals of the addresser, aimed at the interlocutor. In the semantics of the words compliment, there is a common feature - redundancy, exaggeration, which distinguishes the interpretation of compliment and flattery from approval and praise.

Other scientists group speech acts of positive evaluation according to other criteria. Thus, in the taxonomy of J. Austin, the evaluative statements of interest to us, with the exception of the speech acts of approval, refer to habitives - acts of social behavior that express a reaction to a person's behavior, actions [Austin 1962]. The absence of approval in this group is not accidental: statements of approval are aimed at inanimate objects and natural phenomena. In the taxonomy of J. Searle, all speech acts of positive evaluation, apparently, are adjacent to expressives, with the help of which feelings and relationships are expressed: “their illocutionary goal is the expression of a mental state specified in terms of sincerity” [Searle 1979].

Speech acts of approval, praise, compliment and flattery are performed mainly with the aim of expressing a positive assessment. The expression of a positive assessment of an object, its qualities, or activity is a single illocutionary goal invariant for the given speech acts. Another common goal of approving acts, related to their expressive nature, is the need to make a positive impact on the emotions of the addressee, and if the addressee and the object of positive assessment coincide, to induce him in the future to similar states or actions, that is, to those that caused positive evaluation.

In addition to these main goals, addressees of approval, praise, compliment and flattery, to one degree or another, want to create a favorable atmosphere for communication; these speech acts can act as formulas of etiquette, as an expression of politeness, courtesy. Acts of positive evaluation implement strategies of both positive politeness, which prescribes attention to the interlocutor, and negative, requiring, in particular, “to formulate a statement in a softening modal package.” Expressions of a positive assessment can be introduced to mitigate reproach, dissatisfaction, they help politely change the subject, etc.

CONCLUSIONS

So, summarizing the above, we present the following genre-forming features of praise, proposed by O. B. Gorobets:

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1. Realization in a situation of direct / indirect contact, as well as the opportunity to praise not the contacted himself, but his work, the result of his work, achievement, etc.
2. The presence of positively charged style features: respect, recognition.
3. Objective (as far as possible) assessment of the recipient's merits.
4. The possibility and desirability of a response (always positive) - simple gratitude, modesty, a sense of satisfaction.
5. Highly informative nature of the transmitted information due to the seriousness of the topic of praise and its specific referential correlation.
6. Functional orientation - demonstration of approval in order to increase the effectiveness of communication and mutual understanding.

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